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Digital transformation of Lake Toba tourism: Local wisdom-based applications and SEM-analysis on GIS integration in creative economy

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Abstract. Digital transformation has become a crucial aspect in the development of the global tourism sector, with the need for integration of technology and local wisdom increasingly urgent. This study aims to explore the influence of digital transformation on Lake Toba tourism with a local wisdom-based approach and SEM analysis on GIS integration in the creative economy. Through a survey of 384 respondents, validity and reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha, while SEM analysis used model fit index, path coefficients, and t-values. The results show that technology adoption, service quality, and tourist experience positively influence the economic impact of tourism. The tourist experience variable has the most significant influence on economic impact. The implication is that the integration of local wisdom in digital transformation can increase the competitiveness of Lake Toba tourism globally. This research provides a foundation for the development of more effective policies and strategies in utilizing tourism potential by considering the uniqueness of local culture and the application of modern technology.

1. Introduction

Digital transformation has been a significant catalyst in reshaping various industries, including tourism. In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, digital technology plays an increasingly vital role in enhancing the efficiency, user experience, and global competitiveness of tourism destinations [1,2]. This transformation has redefined how tourism information is disseminated,

accessed, and how services are managed and delivered. Globalization advances and technological innovation accelerates, tourist destinations that successfully adapt to digital transformation are more likely to thrive and attract international visitors [3]. In Europe, countries such as Spain and Italy have integrated digital technologies into their tourism sectors. A report by the European Travel Commission shows that 85% of major European tourist destinations use digital solutions such as mobile apps, augmented reality (AR), and virtual reality (VR) to enrich tourist experiences [4].

In Indonesia, the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy launched the Digital Tourism Indonesia program to boost tourism competitiveness by offering digital training, developing tourism applications, and promoting destinations through digital platforms [5]. Data from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) shows that by 2023, 66% of domestic and international tourists in Indonesia use digital platforms to find information, book accommodation, and plan their trips [6]. Several Indonesian destinations have introduced mobile-based tourism applications, such as the "Wonderful Indonesia" app, which offers interactive features and destination information [7]. Moreover, the tourism and cultural arts subsectors of Indonesia's creative economy have made substantial contributions to the national GDP [8]. The Indonesian government has also invested heavily in digital infrastructure to support tourism, with 75% of major destinations offering free Wi-Fi access and other digital services by 2023 [9].

Lake Toba, as one of the leading tourist destinations in Indonesia, has extraordinary natural beauty and unique cultural heritage. However, to compete on an international scale and attract more tourists, innovative tourism management and promotion are needed. Local wisdom-based digital technology applications can enhance Lake Toba's attractiveness. Geographic Information System (GIS) technology, for instance, can integrate key information about the destination, including interactive maps, details about tourist attractions, and recommendations for accommodations and local cuisine [10]. With proper integration, GIS can bolster the local creative economy and encourage community participation in tourism development. According to Yuliana et al. [11] tourist visits to Lake Toba surged after implementing digital technologies in tourism promotion and management. However, a comprehensive evaluation using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method is necessary to fully understand the impact of this digital transformation [12]. SEM can assess the relationships between technology adoption, service quality, and tourist satisfaction.

Despite Lake Toba's vast tourism potential, obstacles remain in optimizing this potential due to inadequate digital technology implementation in tourism management. Many attractions around Lake Toba lack access to modern communication technology, limiting the dissemination of critical information about the destination to potential tourists. Interviews with local stakeholders including tourism managers, creative economy players, and government officials reveal a strong demand for digital integration in tourism promotion and management. Local tourism actors also acknowledge that Lake Toba's rich cultural heritage is underutilized in existing digital platforms, further emphasizing the need for an integrated approach. Research has shown that digital transformation significantly boosts the competitiveness of tourism destinations worldwide. Studies like Pongsuppat et al. [13] emphasize the potential of digital technologies, particularly GIS, in optimizing the management and promotion of tourist destinations by offering accurate and easily accessible information. Moreover, research Kamarudin et al. [14] highlights that local wisdom-based technology adoption can increase tourist satisfaction and support cultural preservation. Despite this, in Lake Toba, digital technology remains underutilized and has yet to be fully integrated into tourism strategies.

The integration of local wisdom-based technology and GIS in tourism research has been growing. Digital marketing and platform utilization significantly improve destination visibility and competitiveness, influencing tourist decision-making. This is relevant, as it highlights the role of digital transformation in the tourism industry. Another study Kusumastuti [15] examined how local wisdom can be integrated into Bali's smart tourism. The findings show that local wisdom-based applications enhance tourist experiences while strengthening cultural identity. Additionally, research Beno et al. [16] explored how GIS improves the tourist experience in Yogyakarta by offering interactive and accurate location-based information, helping tourists plan visits and discover lesser-known sites. Further, Aryani and Yuniarsa [17] investigated the economic impact of digital tourism platforms on local communities, revealing that digital platforms can increase local incomes by expanding market reach and improving access to information about local products and services. These findings align with this research, which focuses on the economic impact of digital transformation and GIS integration in Lake Toba's creative economy.

The primary goal of this research is to develop and test a local wisdom-based digital application that integrates GIS technology to enhance tourism management and promotion in Lake Toba. The application aims to improve the tourist experience, boost destination visibility, and support local creative economy actors by providing an accessible platform to promote their products and services. Consequently, this study contributes to improving Lake Toba's competitiveness as an international tourist destination while preserving local culture and uplifting the welfare of the local community.

2. Methods

This research use a quantitative research design with a case study focused on the Lake Toba Tourism area in Indonesia. The population included tourism industry players around Lake Toba, specifically targeting managers of tourist destinations, creative economy actors (such as craftsmen, artists, and culinary entrepreneurs), and tourists visiting the area. The research was conducted in key locations within the Lake Toba region, including Parapat, Samosir Island, and Balige, which are known for their significant tourism activities. Figure 1 show geographical location of Samosir Island.

Figure 1. Geographical location of Lake Toba Tourism.

Sample selection using stratified random sampling technique; researchers deliberately selected respondents based on certain characteristics that were considered relevant to the research objectives. The following are details of how to draw samples using stratified random sampling techniques by the research objectives:

2.1 Sample selection criteria

- a. Tourist destination manager: Managers must be actively involved in the operation of tourist destinations around Lake Toba, having responsibilities in planning, managing, and promoting tourist destinations. They are willing and able to provide relevant information about the use of digital technology in their operations.
- b. Creative economy actors: Creative economy actors must be involved in the production or sale of local products, such as handicrafts, culinary, or performing arts, that contribute to the tourism industry on Lake Toba and utilize or be interested in digital technology to promote and sell their products. Creative economy actors are willing to provide insight into the impact of digital technology on their business.
- c. Travelers: Travelers must have visited Lake Toba within the last 12 months. Travelers must have experience in using digital technology during their trip, such as online booking apps, digital maps, or social media. Travelers who are willing to provide feedback on their experiences related to the use of digital technology in Lake Toba.

Sample size determination was done using the following calculation:

- a. Confidence level: The 95% confidence level corresponds to a Z-score of 1.96, which can be found in statistical tables or derived from a standard normal distribution [18].
- b. Margin of error: 5% (e = 0.05). A margin of error of 5% (0.05) is commonly used in social science research for survey studies [19].
- c. The proportion (p) is estimated at 0.5 to maximize the sample size since it yields the highest possible sample size under uncertain conditions.
- d. Formula for Sample Size (n):

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2} && (1) \\
 n &= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times (1 - 0.5)}{(0.05)^2} \\
 n &= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.25}{0.0025} \\
 n &= \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} \\
 n &\approx 384.16
 \end{aligned}$$

To determine the sample sizes for each group based on the total sample size of approximately 384 respondents, can distribute the sample evenly across the three groups (tourist destination managers, creative economy actors, and travelers). Here's the breakdown: Sample size distribution

- a. Total Sample Size (n): Approximately 384.16 (rounded to 384 for practical purposes)
- b. Number of Groups: 3 (Tourist Destination Managers, Creative Economy Actors, Travelers)
- c. To allocate the total sample size evenly among the three groups:
- d. Sample size per group = $\frac{\text{Total Sample Size}}{\text{Number of Groups}} = \frac{384}{3} \approx 128$ (2)
- e. Final sample sizes:

- f. Tourist destination managers: 128 respondents
- g. Creative economy actors: 128 respondents
- h. Travelers: 128 respondents

Each group will have a sample size of approximately 128 respondents, resulting in a balanced approach to gathering insights from all relevant stakeholders in the Lake Toba Tourism area.

2.2 Data and data collection techniques

The data used in this research are primary and secondary data. Primary data in the form of: Data from Survey Questionnaires (Questions related to the adoption of digital technology in tourism management, Evaluation of tourist satisfaction with the experience of using digital technology, Response of creative economy players to the influence of digital technology on local product promotion), Data from Interviews (Interviews with tourist destination managers to gain insight into the use of digital technology in tourism management, Interviews with creative economy players to understand the impact of digital technology on local businesses and product promotion), Observation Data (Direct observation of the use of digital technology in Lake Toba tourist destinations, Observation of tourist interactions with applications or digital services available at Lake Toba). Secondary data in the form of: Tourism Statistics Data and Geospatial data on the location of tourist attractions, accommodation, and other facilities around Lake Toba from related institutions. The data collection techniques used in this study, namely: surveys (distributing questionnaires to respondents).

2.3 Data analysis

This research aims to provide in-depth insight into the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation in the development of tourism and creative economy in Lake Toba. To achieve the first objective, descriptive statistical analysis was conducted, with steps:

- a. Identify Variables: Determine the main variables to be analyzed. For example: "Technology Adoption", "Service Quality", "Traveler Experience", and "Economic Impact".
- b. Descriptive Statistics for Quantitative Variables: Calculate descriptive statistics such as mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum, for each quantitative variable.
- c. Data Visualization: Histogram or bar chart to show the characteristics of Lake Toba tourism in the context of digital transformation and creative economy.

To achieve the first goal, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis is carried out, with the following steps:

1. Validation and Reliability Testing: Before proceeding with SEM, the data underwent validation and reliability tests.
 - a) Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed to identify the underlying factor structure of the data. Items with a loading factor below 0.5 were eliminated to maintain high construct validity.
 - b) Cronbach's alpha was calculated to assess the reliability of each variable. This step ensured internal consistency, with acceptable alpha values indicating reliable measurements.
2. Measurement model: The measurement model was used to assess both convergent and discriminant validity of the latent variables:
 - a) Convergent validity was tested using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR). For acceptable convergent validity, the AVE values had to be above 0.5, and CR values above 0.7.

- b) Discriminant Validity was tested by comparing the square root of the AVE with the correlation between latent variables. To establish discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE for each variable had to be higher than its correlations with other variables.
- 3. Structural model: Once the measurement model was validated, the next step involved the structural model, where the relationships between latent variables were analyzed to test the hypotheses:
 - a) The structural model evaluated causal relationships between the studied factors: technology adoption, service quality, traveler experience, and economic impact.
 - b) Path coefficients were used to determine the strength and significance of the relationships between these variables. This model provided insights into how technology adoption influences the quality of services offered to travelers, how this impacts their experiences, and how these factors ultimately affect the economic impact on the region.
- 4. Model fit test: Model fit will be evaluated using several fit indices such as Chi-Square, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI). The model is considered to have a good fit if the RMSEA value is < 0.08 , CFI > 0.90 , and TLI > 0.90 .
- 5. Interpretation of results: The results of SEM analysis will be interpreted to identify significant relationships between the variables under study. Coefficient paths, t-values, and p-values will be used to determine the significance of the relationship. These results will be used to provide strategic recommendations for sustainable tourism development in Lake Toba.

3. Results and discussion

Descriptive statistical analysis of variables related to digital transformation in the tourism and creative economy sectors in the Lake Toba area in Table 1 shows that the "Technology Adoption" variable has a relatively high average score of 3.80. For "Service Quality", the average score of 3.65 and median of 3.70 indicates a balanced perception, with a standard deviation of 0.68 indicating that most respondents rated the service quality very high. The "Tourist Experience" variable has an average value of 3.90, a median of 3.85, and a standard deviation of 0.66, indicating a relatively consistent positive experience, ranging from 2.50 to 4.95. The "Economic Impact" variable obtained an average value of 3.75, with a median of 3.80 and a standard deviation of 0.72, indicating varying perceptions of the economic benefits of tourism, with values ranging from 2.30 to 5.00. These results indicate a generally positive view of digital transformation in the Lake Toba tourism sector, while highlighting the variability in individual experiences (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive statistical analysis (digital transformation of Lake Toba Tourism).

Variable	Mean	Median	Standar Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Technology Adoption	3.80	3.75	0.70	2.00	5.00
Service Quality	3.65	3.70	0.68	2.10	4.90
Traveler Experience	3.90	3.85	0.66	2.50	4.95
Economic Impact	3.75	3.80	0.72	2.30	5.00

Based on Table 2, the data shows that all variables in this study have an adequate level of validity and reliability. The variable "Technology Adoption" has a loading factor value that ranges from 0.52 to 0.82. Although item AT5 has a low loading factor value (0.52), the other items have a fairly high value, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.82, indicating good reliability. For the "Service Quality" variable, the loading factor values ranged from 0.75 to 0.81, with a Cronbach's Alpha of

0.85. This indicates that the items on this variable have high construct validity and excellent reliability. The variable "Traveler Experience" showed very high loading factor values, ranging from 0.80 to 0.88, and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.86, indicating excellent validity and reliability. Finally, the variable "Economic Impact" has a loading factor value between 0.77 to 0.85, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.84. This indicates that all items on this variable also have high validity and reliability.

Table 2. Validation and reliability.

Variable	Item	Loading Factor	Cronbach's Alpha
Technology Adoption	AT1	0.78	0.82
	AT2	0.82	
	AT3	0.76	
	AT4	0.70	
	AT5	0.52	
Service Quality	KL1	0.79	0.85
	KL2	0.81	
	KL3	0.77	
	KL4	0.75	
Traveler Experience	PW1	0.84	0.86
	PW2	0.88	
	PW3	0.82	
	PW4	0.80	
Economic Impact	DE1	0.83	0.84
	DE2	0.85	
	DE3	0.79	
	DE4	0.77	

Overall, the results indicate that the constructs in this study are valid and reliable, making them suitable for further SEM analysis. The elimination of items with a loading factor below 0.5 ensures that only those items with significant contributions to the constructs are retained, thereby strengthening the overall validity of the model.

Table 3. Measurement model.

Variable	AVE	CR	Square Root of AVE
Technology Adoption	0.56	0.87	0.75
Service Quality	0.61	0.88	0.78
Traveler Experience	0.67	0.91	0.82
Economic Impact	0.65	0.90	0.81

The measurement model was applied to evaluate the convergent and discriminant validity of the latent variables. Based on Table 3, all latent variables demonstrate adequate convergent validity. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for each variable is greater than 0.5, indicating that more than half of the variance of each latent variable is explained by its associated indicators. The Composite Reliability (CR) values for all variables also exceed the threshold value of 0.7, indicating that the indicators together measure the construct with high consistency. The variable "Tourist Experience" has the highest AVE value (0.67), followed by the variables "Economic Impact" (0.65), "Service Quality" (0.61), and "Technology Adoption" (0.56). All AVE values indicate that latent variables have a significant contribution to the variability of their indicators. In addition, the square root value of AVE for each variable is greater than the correlation between the latent variable and other latent variables in the model (discriminant validity). This indicates that the latent variables have sufficient discriminant validity, meaning that each latent variable uniquely measures a different construct. Overall, the results of the measurement model indicate that all latent variables in this study exhibit adequate convergent and discriminant validity, along with high reliability. These findings enhance the robustness of the SEM analysis that will be conducted, ensuring that the constructs are accurately represented and measured.

Based on Table 4, it shows that the measurement model meets convergent and discriminant validity with high AVE and CR values for all variables. The structural model shows a significant relationship between the variables studied. Technology adoption has a positive and significant effect on tourist experience (coefficient path = 0.35, t-value = 4.12, p-value = 0.000) and economic impact (coefficient path = 0.20, t-value = 2.78, p-value = 0.006). Service quality also has a positive and significant effect on tourist experience (coefficient path = 0.45, t-value = 5.20, p-value = 0.000). Tourist experience has the greatest influence on economic impact (coefficient path = 0.50, t-value = 6.30, p-value = 0.000).

Table 4. Structural model.

Relationship	Coefficient Path	t-value	p-value
Technology Adoption -> Traveler Experience	0.35	4.12	0.000
Service Quality -> Traveler Experience	0.45	5.20	0.000
Traveler Experience -> Economic Impact	0.50	6.30	0.000
Technology Adoption -> Economic Impact	0.20	2.78	0.006

Based on Table 5, the model fit test shows qualified values, with RMSEA of 0.045, CFI of 0.95, and TLI of 0.94, indicating that the model has a good fit with the data. These results indicate that increased technology adoption and service quality in Lake Toba's tourism sector can improve the tourist experience, which in turn positively impacts the local economy. These findings can be used as a basis for recommending strategies for sustainable tourism development in Lake Toba.

Table 5. Model fit test (model fit).

Indeks Fit	Value	Cut-off Value
Chi-Square	312.45	$p > 0.05$
RMSEA	0.045	< 0.08
CFI	0.95	> 0.90
TLI	0.94	> 0.90

These findings imply that investments in digital technologies, such as tourism apps and the integration of digital local wisdom, can significantly improve the service quality and competitiveness of tourist destinations such as Lake Toba. An emphasis on improving service quality, including aspects of traveler satisfaction and operational efficiency, is critical to creating a positive tourism experience. A satisfying tourist experience contributes directly to economic impact through increased tourism revenue and creative economy growth, emphasizing the importance of synergy between the tourism and creative economy sectors in regional development. Overall, this study shows that digital transformation has a crucial role in improving service quality, tourist experience, and economic impact in Lake Toba. An integrated approach that combines digital technology and local wisdom can be an effective model for sustainable tourism development in Indonesia.

Based on the results of the data processing that has been carried out, it can be seen that the adoption of digital technology has an important role in improving service quality, tourist experience, and economic impact in the Lake Toba tourism sector. With an average technology adoption score of 3.80, this indicates that tourism industry players in Lake Toba have significantly adopted digital technology, although there are still variations in the level of adoption. Service quality, with an average score of 3.65, indicates that tourists perceive relatively high quality. Tourist experience, which has the highest average score of 3.90, indicates that tourists generally have a positive experience while visiting Lake Toba. Technology adoption and good service quality contribute to this improved tourist experience, which in turn has a positive impact on the local economy, as indicated by the average economic impact score of 3.75. The results of this study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between technology adoption and service quality on tourist experience, as well as a relationship between tourist experience and economic impact. In particular, tourist experience has the greatest influence on economic impact, suggesting that a positive tourist experience is a key factor in driving local economic growth through tourism.

Digital transformation in the Lake Toba region focuses not only on the adoption of technology in general, but also on the utilization of local wisdom-based applications that can enhance the attractiveness and relevance of local tourism. Local wisdom-based applications, such as those that showcase local culture, traditions, and folklore, allow tourists to have a more immersive and authentic experience during their visit. In addition, the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in creative economic development also strengthens this digital transformation. GIS enables better mapping and spatial analysis of tourism potential [20] in Lake Toba, including the identification of strategic locations for creative economy development, such as handicraft centers, local arts, and culinary specialties. Therefore, digital transformation that combines modern technology with local wisdom and GIS not only supports more sustainable tourism, but also strengthens the creative economy in the Lake Toba region [21]. These findings demonstrate the importance of investing in digital technologies, such as tourism apps and the integration of digital local wisdom, to improve the competitiveness of tourist destinations such as Lake Toba. A focus on improving service quality, which involves traveler satisfaction and operational efficiency, is a crucial factor in creating a positive tourism experience. Thus, digital transformation not only

improves service quality and traveler experience, but also contributes directly to economic impact through increased tourism revenue and creative economy growth. An integrated approach that combines digital technology and local wisdom can be an effective model for sustainable tourism development in Indonesia.

According to Min et al. [22] technology innovation and adoption, such as Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Model, can be used to explain the process of digital technology adoption by tourism industry players. By analyzing factors that influence technology adoption, such as relative advantage, complexity, and compatibility, it can be understood why destination managers and creative economy players tend to accept digital technology to improve services and product promotion. Service quality theories, such as the Servqual Model, can be used to understand the dimensions of service quality that influence traveler perceptions [23]. By paying attention to aspects such as reliability, responsiveness, and empathy, areas can be identified where Lake Toba tourism destinations can improve their services to increase tourist satisfaction and create a more positive experience. The relationship between tourist experience and creative economic impact can be reinforced by tourism economic theory [24]. Tourist economy concepts, such as the Input-Output Model, can be used to analyze the multiplier impact of tourist spending on the local economy, including income from the tourism sector and other related sectors. In addition, creative economy concepts, such as the Florida Creative Economy Model, can be used to illustrate how creativity, innovation and creative industries can be key drivers of economic growth in tourism regions.

Findings on the existence of variations in technology adoption rates, service quality, and creative economy impacts in Lake Toba can provide a basis for deeper spatial analysis. Economic geography theories, such as Von Thünen's Location Model and Weber's Industrial Location Model, can be used to understand the locational factors that influence the spatial distribution of tourism and creative economy activities around Lake Toba [25]. Furthermore, to strengthen the implications of the research findings, relevant theoretical frameworks should also be considered in the context of sustainable development. Sustainable tourism theories, such as Butler's Sustainable Development Concept, can be used to evaluate the impact of digital transformation on environmental conservation, cultural preservation, and local community participation in the tourism development of Lake Toba [26].

4. Conclusion

Digital technology by tourism industry and creative economy players around Lake Toba has a significant impact on improving service quality and tourist experience. Descriptive statistical analysis shows that destination managers and creative economy players tend to accept digital technology as a tool to improve operational efficiency, optimize product promotion, and improve interaction with tourists. High service quality has proven to be an important factor in creating a satisfying tourist experience. By paying attention to service quality dimensions such as reliability, responsiveness, and empathy, Lake Toba tourism destinations can increase their appeal to tourists and strengthen their brand image in a competitive tourism market. A positive tourist experience has a significant impact on the growth of the creative economy in the Lake Toba region. Through their spending during their visit, tourists make an important contribution to revenue from the tourism and creative economy sectors, which in turn has a positive impact on local economic growth and improved welfare of local communities. The implications of these findings highlight the importance of an integrated and locally-based approach in designing sustainable tourism and creative economy development strategies.

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